

Rationalization and tuning of doublet emission in organic radicals

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List of contents

Radical-ligand interactions

Figure S1. Molecular structure of TTM-like model system **0** for $\theta = 90^\circ$ and molecular orbital diagram.

Table S1. Vertical transition energies (in eV) to the lowest excited doublet states, oscillator strength, and dominant contributions computed at the PBE0/6-311G(d,p) level for **0** at $\theta = 90^\circ$.

Figure S2. Evolution of the energy of the SOMO/SUMO (green/purple) and HOMO/LUMO (in grey) of **0** as a function of the dihedral angle θ .

Diabatization of the adiabatic states at the ground state (D_3) geometry of **1**

Table S2. e-/h+ contributions to the relative Mulliken fragment charges of diabatic states Z_{1-4} .

Table S3. Energy (in eV) and transition dipole moment components (in D) of diabatic states Z_{1-4} .

Diabatic Hamiltonian (ground state (D_3) geometry)

Excited state relaxation

Table S4. Bonds and dihedrals at the D_3 and C_2 geometries.

Table S5. Vertical transition energies (in eV) to the lowest excited doublet states, oscillator strength, dominant contributions and transition dipole moment components (in D) computed at the PBE0/6-311G(d,p) level at the C_2 geometry.

Diabatization of the adiabatic states computed at the D_1 optimized geometry of **1**

Table S6. e-/h+ contributions to the relative Mulliken fragment charges of diabatic states Z_{1-4} .

Figure S3. TTM molecule with vector representation of TDMs of Z_{1-4} diabatic states at the lowest excited state (C_2) geometry of **1**.

Table S7. Energy (in eV) and transition dipole moment components (in D) of diabatic states Z_{1-4} at the lowest excited state (C_2) geometry of **1**.

Substituted TTM

Figure S4. Energy of the SOMO/SUMO (green/purple) and HOMO/LUMO (in grey) for **1**, **1NO₂**, **1NH₂**, **1'NH₂**, and **1''NH₂**.

Radical-ligand interactions

Figure S1. Molecular structure of TTM-like model system **0** for $\theta = 90^\circ$ and molecular orbital diagram.

Table S1. Vertical transition energies (in eV) to the lowest excited doublet states, oscillator strength, and dominant contributions computed at the PBE0/6-311G(d,p) level for **0** at $\theta = 90^\circ$.

state	E	f	contributions	coeff
1 (A_1'')	3.820	0	88B \rightarrow 89B	0.99044
5 (E'')	4.182	0	86B \rightarrow 89B	0.97606
6 (E'')	4.182	0	87B \rightarrow 89B	0.97606
7 (E'')	4.285	0	89A \rightarrow 91A	0.99235
8 (E'')	4.285	0	89A \rightarrow 90A	0.99235

reported contributions ≥ 0.2 only

Figure S2. Evolution of the energy of the SOMO/SUMO (green/purple) and HOMO/LUMO (in grey) of **0** as a function of the dihedral angle θ .

Diabatization of the adiabatic states at the ground state (D_3) geometry of **1**

Table S2. e-/h+ contributions to the relative Mulliken fragment charges of diabatic states Z_{1-4} .

state	Z_1 (LC _x)		Z_2 (LC _y)		Z_3 (CL _y)		Z_4 (CL _x)	
	β h+	β e-	β h+	β e-	α h+	α e-	α h+	α e-
central C	0.011	-0.442	0.011	-0.442	0.262	-0.024	0.262	-0.024
ligand (1)	0.322	-0.178	0.322	-0.178	0.194	-0.274	0.194	-0.274
ligand (2)	0.122	-0.173	0.522	-0.184	0.258	-0.477	0.131	-0.070
ligand (3)	0.522	-0.184	0.122	-0.173	0.131	-0.070	0.258	-0.477

Table S3. Energy (in eV) and transition dipole moment components (in D) of diabatic states Z_{1-4} .

	E	TDM(x)	TDM(y)	TDM(z)
Z_1 (LC _x)	3.043	2.258	-2.258	0.000
Z_2 (LC _y)	3.043	-2.258	-2.258	0.000
Z_3 (CL _y)	3.458	2.057	2.057	0.000
Z_4 (CL _x)	3.458	-2.057	2.057	0.000

Diabatic Hamiltonian (ground state (D_3) geometry)

diabatic H	Z1	Z2	Z3	Z4
Z1	3.043	0.000	0.000	-0.278
Z2	0.000	3.043	-0.278	0.000
Z3	0.000	-0.278	3.458	0.000
Z4	-0.278	0.000	0.000	3.458

Excited state relaxation

Table S4. Bonds and dihedrals at the D_3 and C_2 geometries.

	D_3 geometry	C_2 geometry
θ_1	49.7	45.1
θ_2	49.7	44.3
θ_3	49.7	43.8
b_1	1.470	1.428
b_2	1.470	1.454
b_3	1.470	1.454
a	1.407	1.458
d / g	1.407	1.414
b	1.382	1.364
e / h	1.382	1.379
c	1.382	1.399
f / i	1.382	1.386

Table S5. Vertical transition energies (in eV) to the lowest excited doublet states, oscillator strength, dominant contributions and transition dipole moment components (in D) computed at the PBE0/6-311G(d,p) level at the C_2 geometry.

state	E	f	contributions	coeff	TDM(x)	TDM(y)	TDM(z)
D₁ (E)	2.421	0.035	137A→138A 136B→137B	-0.300 0.930	0	-0.769	0
D₂ (E)	2.673	0.034	137A→139A 135B→137B	-0.262 0.936	0.723	0	-0.044
D₇ (E)	3.319	0.273	137A→138A 133B→137B 136B→137B	0.816 0.366 0.279	0	-1.833	0
D₈ (E)	3.480	0.251	137A→139A	0.854	1.715	0	0.002

132B→137B -0.274
 135B→137B 0.271

Diabatization of the adiabatic states at the lowest excited state (C_2) geometry of **1**

Table S6. e-/h+ contributions to the relative Mulliken fragment charges of diabatic states Z_{1-4} .

state	Z_1		Z_2		Z_3		Z_4	
	β h+	β e-	β h+	β e-	α h+	α e-	α h+	α e-
central C	0.018	-0.377	0.009	-0.374	0.215	-0.019	0.242	-0.019
ligand (1)	0.641	-0.229	0.108	-0.229	0.301	-0.504	0.174	-0.029
ligand (2)	0.156	-0.183	0.431	-0.189	0.140	-0.136	0.221	-0.405
ligand (3)	0.156	-0.183	0.431	-0.189	0.140	-0.136	0.221	-0.405

Figure S3. TTM molecule with vector representation of TDMs of Z_{1-4} diabatic states at the lowest excited state (C_2) geometry of **1**.

Table S7. Energy (in eV) and transition dipole moment components (in D) of diabatic states Z_{1-4} at the lowest excited state (C_2) geometry of **1**.

	E	TDM(x)	TDM(y)	TDM(z)
Z_1	2.421	0.000	3.968	0.000
Z_2	2.673	-3.451	0.000	0.100
Z_3	3.108	0.000	3.126	0.000
Z_4	3.347	-3.236	0.000	-0.050

Diabatic Hamiltonian (C_2 geometry)

diabatic H	Z_1	Z_2	Z_3	Z_4
Z_1	2.632	0.000	0.381	0.000
Z_2	0.000	2.807	0.000	0.300
Z_3	0.381	0.000	3.108	0.000
Z_4	0.000	0.300	0.000	3.347

Substituted TTM

Figure S4. Energy of the SOMO/SUMO (green/purple) and HOMO/LUMO (in grey) for 1, 1NO₂, 1NH₂, 1'NH₂, and 1''NH₂.